

1 **SHMT inhibition is effective and synergizes with methotrexate in T-cell acute**
2 **lymphoblastic leukemia**

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42 Rabinowitz are inventors on a Princeton University patent covering serine

43 hydroxymethyltransferase inhibitors and their use in cancer. J. D. Rabinowitz is a co-founder of

44 Raze Therapeutics and advisor and stock owner in Kadmon, Agios, L.E.A.F., and Rafael

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46 **Abstract**

47 Folate metabolism enables cell growth by providing one-carbon (1C) units for nucleotide
48 biosynthesis. The 1C units are carried by tetrahydrofolate (THF), whose production by the
49 enzyme DHFR is targeted by the important anticancer drug methotrexate. 1C units come largely
50 from serine catabolism by the enzyme SHMT, whose mitochondrial isoform is strongly
51 upregulated in cancer. Here we report the SHMT inhibitor SHIN2 and demonstrate its *in vivo*
52 target engagement with ¹³C-serine tracing. As methotrexate is standard treatment for T-cell acute
53 lymphoblastic leukemia (T-ALL), we explored the utility of SHIN2 in this disease. SHIN2
54 increases survival in NOTCH1-driven mouse primary T-ALL *in vivo*. Low dose methotrexate
55 sensitizes Molt4 human T-ALL cells to SHIN2, and cells rendered methotrexate resistant *in vitro*
56 show enhanced sensitivity to SHIN2. Finally, SHIN2 and methotrexate synergize in mouse
57 primary T-ALL and in a human patient-derived xenograft *in vivo*, increasing survival. Thus,
58 SHMT inhibition offers a complementary strategy in the treatment of T-ALL.

59 **Introduction**

60 One-carbon (1C) metabolism, mediated by the folate cofactor, enables cancer growth and
61 proliferation by supporting purine and pyrimidine biosynthesis, as well as amino acid
62 homeostasis (glycine, serine, and methionine), epigenetic maintenance, and redox defense (ref.
63 1–7). In rapidly proliferating cells including cancer cells, the amino acid serine is the main 1C
64 donor (ref. 4,8–11). The enzyme serine hydroxymethyltransferase (SHMT), which has cytosolic
65 (SHMT1) and mitochondrial (SHMT2) isoforms, catalyzes the conversion of serine and
66 tetrahydrofolate (THF) into glycine and 5,10-methylene-THF (ref. 1,12–14). Consistent with
67 their key role in providing 1C units for DNA synthesis, the 1C/folate metabolism enzymes
68 SHMT2 and the immediately downstream mitochondrial enzyme 5,10-methylene-
69 tetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase (MTHFD2) are among the most consistently overexpressed
70 metabolic enzymes in cancer (ref. 15–17).

71 Due to the existence of functionally redundant mitochondrial and cytosolic 1C/folate
72 metabolism branches (ref. 1,4), single deletion of key enzymes (e.g. SHMT1, SHMT2,
73 MTHFD1L, MTHFD2) does not block cell proliferation under nutrient replete conditions (ref.
74 4,18,19). Double deletion of SHMT1/SHMT2 or SHMT1/MTHDF2, however, completely halts
75 proliferation under standard culture conditions *in vitro* and tumor growth *in vivo* (ref. 4,18).

76 Motivated by this genetic evidence, we developed a dual SHMT1/2 inhibitor. Building from
77 a pyrazolopyran scaffold that inhibits plant SHMT, we designed SHIN1, a folate-competitive
78 cell-permeable inhibitor of human SHMT1/2 (ref. 18). SHIN1 demonstrates potent and specific
79 on target activity against SHMT in HCT116 cells and inhibits proliferation across a wide range
80 of cancer cell lines (ref. 18). Due to rapid clearance, however, SHIN1 is not suitable for *in vivo*
81 studies.

82 Here we present SHIN2, the first *in vivo* active mammalian SHMT1/2 inhibitor. We validate
83 the *in vitro* and *in vivo* on target activity against SHMT using metabolomics and isotope tracing,
84 and apply SHIN2 in the context of T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia (T-ALL). The
85 dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) inhibitor methotrexate is a standard of care treatment in both
86 pediatric and adult T-ALL (ref. 20,21). Despite advances in treatments, 20-50% of the T-ALL
87 patients relapse. The prognosis of these T-ALL patients remains extremely poor, highlighting the
88 need to discover novel therapeutic approaches (ref. 22,23).

89 SHIN2 inhibits proliferation in human T-ALL cell lines and has an antileukemic effect *in*
90 *vivo* in a mouse model of NOTCH1-driven T-ALL and in a patient derived T-ALL xenograft.
91 Interestingly, SHIN2 shows a synergistic activity when combined with methotrexate both *in vitro*
92 and *in vivo*. Moreover, methotrexate-resistant human T-ALL cells showed increased sensitivity
93 to SHIN2. Thus, here we present a novel drug suitable for dual SHMT1/2 inhibition *in vivo* and
94 demonstrate that targeting SHMT is effective for the treatment of T-ALL, alone or in
95 combination with DHFR inhibition, and might be useful in patients with methotrexate-resistant
96 disease.

97 **Materials and Methods**

98 *Cell lines, reagents, constructs and antibodies*

99 Human colon cancer cell line HCT116 and human T-ALL cell lines Molt4, Molt3, Jurkat and
100 KOPT-K1 were obtained from ATCC. HPBALL and DND41 human T-ALL cell lines were
101 obtained from DSMZ (The Leibniz Institute). The CUTLL1 NOTCH1-dependent T-cell
102 lymphoblastic cell line has been previously described (ref. 24). SHMT1 and SHMT2 were
103 knocked out in HCT116 lines using CRISPR/Cas9 nickase method as previously described (ref.
104 4,18). Adherent cell lines were subcultured in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C using DMEM (CellGro 10–017;
105 Mediatech) supplemented with 10% FBS (F2442; Sigma-Aldrich); suspension cell lines were
106 subcultured in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C in RPMI-1640 (11875; Gibco) with 10% FBS, 100 U/ml
107 penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin. For all experiments, media supplemented with 10%
108 dialyzed FBS was used (F0392; Sigma-Aldrich). Cell lines were regularly tested for
109 mycoplasma. Antibodies were used according to their manufacturers' directions. Anti-SHMT1
110 (12612) and SHMT2 (12762) were obtained from Cell Signaling Technologies (1:1,000
111 dilution). Anti-β-ACTIN (A3854) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (1:50,000 dilution).
112 Secondary antibody coupled to horseradish peroxidase (NA934) was obtained from Sigma-
113 Aldrich. Signal was detected using enhanced chemiluminescence (34578, Thermo Scientific).

114 *In vivo target engagement of SHIN2 in mice*

115 Mouse studies followed protocols approved by the Princeton University Institutional Animal
116 Care and Use Committee. Infusion was performed on single-housed 10 - 14 week old male
117 C57BL/6 mice with a catheter surgically implanted on the right jugular vein (Charles River). U-
118 ¹³C-Serine was prepared at 30 mM in saline and infused at 0.1 µL/min/g. (+)SHIN2 was
119 prepared at 20 mg/ml in a 20% 2-hydroxypropyl-β-cyclodextrin solution in water. Mice received

120 either vehicle or a single dose of (+)SHIN2 (200 mg/kg) via an intraperitoneal (IP) injection at
121 the beginning of the experiment. Blood (~10 µL) was collected by tail bleeding in blood
122 collection tubes (Sarstedt 16.443.100), placed on ice for 20 min, and centrifuged at 16,000 g for
123 10 min at 4 °C to obtain serum and then kept at -80 °C until LC-MS analysis.

124 *In vivo efficacy of SHIN2 in NOTCH1-driven mouse T-ALL and patient derived xenografts*

125 Animals were maintained in specific pathogen-free facilities at the Rutgers Cancer Institute
126 of New Jersey. The Rutgers Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) approved
127 all animal procedures. Generation of NOTCH1-induced T-ALL tumors in mice has been
128 previously described (ref. 25). Animals were randomly assigned to the different treatment
129 groups, and investigators were not blinded to group allocation. Sample size was estimated based
130 on previous reports (ref. 25). For survival studies, leukemia cells expressing a fusion protein
131 consisting of the cherry fluorescent protein fused to luciferase (MigR1-mCherry-Luc) were
132 transplanted from primary recipients into sublethally irradiated C57BL/6 (4.5 Gy) secondary
133 recipients (Taconic Farms) (ref. 25). Animals were monitored for signs of illness, injury or
134 abnormal behavior at least twice daily. Terminally ill leukemic animals were euthanized
135 according to humane endpoints approved by Rutgers IACUC, including: body condition scoring
136 (BCS) < 1,5, rough hair coat, hunched posture, lethargy, abnormal breathing, central nervous
137 system signs (head tilt, spasticity or paralysis) and/or unresponsiveness to external stimuli. For *in*
138 *vivo* drug dosing, (+)SHIN2 was dissolved at 20 mg/mL in a 20% 2-hydroxypropyl-β-
139 cyclodextrin solution in water, and methotrexate at 1 mg/mL in PBS. Methotrexate was
140 administered at 10 mg/kg (IP injection), (+)SHIN2 was administered at 200 mg/kg (IP injection).
141 For the investigation of (+)SHIN2 as a single agent, mice were dosed BID with vehicle or
142 (+)SHIN2 for 11 days. For the drug synergism studies in mouse primary T-ALL *in vivo*, we

143 treated the mice with 4 cycles of intraperitoneal doses of day 1 methotrexate (10 mg/kg) and
144 (+)SHIN2 or vehicle; days 2 to 4 two doses daily of (+)SHIN2 or vehicle, day 5 methotrexate
145 (10 mg/kg) or vehicle, and 2 days off. We evaluated disease progression and therapy response by
146 *in vivo* bioimaging with the *In vivo* Imaging System (IVIS, Xenogen). To investigate potential
147 toxicity from the combination of methotrexate and (+)SHIN2 *in vivo*, healthy C57BL6 mice were
148 treated with 2 cycles of methotrexate alone or in combination with (+)SHIN2 (BID). For the
149 experiment using a human primary leukemia xenograft, we used a previously reported xenograft
150 (PDTALL#10) expressing the cherry fluorescent protein and luciferase (FUW-mCherry-Puro-
151 Luc) (ref. 25); cells were injected into male or female 8 - 10 week old NRG mice (the Jackson
152 Laboratory). Mice were treated with two cycles of 11 days of treatment with (+)SHIN2 (BID) or
153 vehicle. Mice were left off-treatment for 11 days between cycle 1 and cycle 2. Methotrexate (10
154 mg/kg) was injected the day before each (+)SHIN2 cycle started, and at day 6 of each cycle. We
155 evaluated disease progression and therapy response by *in vivo* bioimaging with the *In vivo*
156 Imaging System (IVIS, Xenogen).

157 ***Human primary xenografts***

158 T-ALL samples were provided by the University of Padova. Written consent was obtained at
159 study entry and samples were collected under the supervision of local Institutional Review
160 Boards for participating institutions and analyzed under the supervision of Rutgers University.

161 ***Statistical Analyses***

162 Statistical analyses were performed with Prism 7.0 (GraphPad) or R (ref. 26). Statistical
163 significance between conditions was calculated using an unpaired two-tailed Student's t test
164 when comparing two groups or ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc analysis when comparing
165 more than two. Samples sizes, error bars, and p values are defined in each figure legend. Survival

166 in mouse experiments was represented with Kaplan-Meier curves, and significance was
167 estimated with the log-rank test. Synergy *in vivo* was estimated using a Cox regression
168 introducing an interaction term using a Firth's penalized maximum likelihood bias reduction
169 method. Synergy *in vitro* was estimated by representing the IC₅₀ isobolograms.

170 Additional methods (proliferation assays, cell cycle and apoptosis analyses, flow cytometry
171 analysis of T-cell development, measurement of hematological parameters, cell metabolism
172 studies, metabolite extraction, LC-MS-based untargeted metabolomics analysis, and chemical
173 synthesis of SHIN2) are described in the supplementary information (Supplementary Materials
174 and Methods).

175 **Results**

176 *A small-molecule inhibitor of SHMT1/2 with in vivo target engagement.*

177 We previously described SHIN1, a folate-competitive inhibitor of human SHMT1/2 (ref. 18).
178 SHIN1 showed potent and specific cell-based target engagement and inhibited proliferation in a
179 wide range of human cancer cell lines (ref. 18). SHIN1, however, lacked pharmacokinetic
180 properties suitable for *in vivo* study of SHMT biology. To improve on SHIN1's half-life, we
181 synthesized a series of related molecules with different substitutions on the phenyl ring, leading
182 to the discovery of an inhibitor with improved pharmacokinetic properties, SHIN2 (Fig. 1a).

183 We next investigated the activity of SHIN2 in cultured cells. SHIN2 blocked proliferation of
184 HCT116 Ras-driven colon cancer cells, in a stereoselective manner, with a half-maximal
185 inhibitory constant (IC₅₀) of 300 nM for the (+) enantiomer. Proliferation was restored by the
186 addition of 1 mM formate, which provides 1C units independently of SHMT activity (Fig. 1b).
187 Knockout of SHMT2, which is the dominant SHMT isozyme in most cancer cells, but not
188 SHMT1, sensitized HCT116 to (+)SHIN2 (Fig. S1a). Metabolomic analysis of HCT116 cells
189 treated with (+)SHIN2, but not (-)SHIN2, revealed metabolic alterations consistent with SHMT
190 inhibition, which were largely reversed by exogenous formate (Fig. S1b-d). These included
191 dTTP and ATP depletion and serine and purine biosynthetic intermediates buildup, specifically
192 the accumulation of purine intermediates directly preceding 1C-dependent reactions (AICAR,
193 GAR) (Fig. 1c, Fig. S1b).

194 To evaluate (+)SHIN2 target engagement *in vivo*, we developed an assay based on
195 continuous infusion of tracer amounts of [U-¹³C]-serine (which contains three ¹³C atoms and
196 accordingly is M+3) and monitoring of circulating serine and glycine labeling by mass
197 spectrometry (Fig. 1d). SHMT activity converts M+3 serine into M+2 glycine and M+1

198 methylene-THF. Due to SHMT reversibility, the M+2 glycine can recombine with an unlabeled
199 1C unit from methylene-THF to give rise to M+2 serine; similarly, unlabeled glycine can
200 recombine with a labeled 1C unit to give rise to M+1 serine (Fig. 1e). IP administration of 200
201 mg/kg (+)SHIN2 resulted in micromolar plasma levels, which were sufficient to impair SHMT
202 activity for 8 h, based on decreased circulating M+1 and M+2 serine and M+2 glycine (Fig. 1f-i).
203 Thus, (+)SHIN2 blocks SHMT both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

204 ***SHIN2 blocks T-ALL growth by inhibiting SHMT***

205 We then sought tumor types with particular sensitivity to 1C/folate pathway inhibition.
206 Analysis of publicly available data revealed that ALL cell lines show the highest sensitivity, of a
207 wide range of cancer types, for both the DHFR inhibitor methotrexate (ref. 27) (Fig. S2a) and an
208 earlier generation SHMT inhibitor (ref. 18) (Fig. S2b). Moreover, methotrexate is frequently
209 used in the treatment of T-ALL (ref. 20,21). In addition, human T-ALL cell lines show increased
210 expression of SHMT2 compared to normal hematological cells (i.e. human thymus, peripheral
211 blood mononuclear cells and peripheral blood CD4+ T cells) (Fig. S2c). MYC has been
212 previously shown to directly regulate SHMT1/2 (ref. 28–30). Moreover, the NOTCH1-MYC
213 axis is critical for T-ALL growth, as over 60% of T-ALLs harbor activating mutations of
214 NOTCH1 (ref. 31), and one of the critical functions of NOTCH1 in T-ALL generation and
215 progression is to directly activate MYC through the distal N-Me enhancer (ref. 32–34). Thus, it
216 is likely that SHMT2 is overexpressed in T-ALL, at least in part, via NOTCH1-MYC. Consistent
217 with this hypothesis, NOTCH1 inhibition in T-ALL *in vivo* translates into reduced levels of
218 *Shmt1/2*, independently of *Pten* mutational status (ref. 25) (Fig. S2d). Moreover, acute deletion
219 of the N-Me enhancer in mouse T-ALLs *in vivo* leads to a drastic reduction in Myc levels (ref.

220 33), which translates into significant downregulation of both *Shmt1/2* (Fig. S2e). Therefore, we
221 decided to analyze the effect of (+)SHIN2 in the treatment of T-ALL.

222 (+)SHIN2 inhibited proliferation across various human T-ALL cell lines (Fig. S2f), and was
223 particularly potent against the human T-ALL cell line Molt4 ($IC_{50} \sim 90$ nM) (Fig. 2a), a
224 prototypical T-ALL cell line harboring activating mutations in NOTCH1 (ref. 31). Addition of
225 formate to culture media rescued proliferation of cells treated with (+)SHIN2 (Fig. 2a). Next,
226 analysis of cell proliferation and apoptosis in Molt4 and other T-ALL cell lines treated with
227 (+)SHIN2 revealed that its antiproliferative effect is mainly cytostatic, characterized by a block
228 in S phase of the cell cycle, with little induction of cytotoxicity (Fig. 2b and Fig. S2g-h).

229 As in the case of HCT116, untargeted LC-MS analysis of water-soluble metabolites showed
230 that the changes induced by (+)SHIN2 were consistent with on-target SHMT inhibition, and
231 most of them were reversed by formate (Fig. 2c-d, Fig. S2i-j). Interestingly, in T-ALL cell lines,
232 (+)SHIN2 not only induced an increase in the purine biosynthesis intermediates GAR and
233 AICAR, which require 1C units to be further metabolized, but also in phosphoribosyl
234 pyrophosphate (PRPP), which is upstream of a step requiring glycine, which is also a product of
235 the SHMT reaction (Fig. 2e, Fig. S2i-j). Consistent with (+)SHIN2 reducing functional glycine
236 availability, formate addition normalized GAR and AICAR, but not PRPP and induced a more
237 acute decrease in intracellular glycine (Fig. 2c-e, Fig. S2i-j).

238 Inhibition of cellular SHMT activity can be further monitored by isotope tracing using [U-
239 ^{13}C]-serine as a tracer (Fig. 2f). (+)SHIN2 achieved a nearly complete blockade of SHMT
240 activity as evidenced by the decrease in M+1 and M+2 serine, M+2 glycine, and the
241 incorporation of serine-derived glycine and 1C units into ATP, GTP and dTTP (M+1 – M+4
242 ATP and GTP and M+1 dTTP) (Fig. 2g). Consistent with SHMT activity being the main route to

243 intracellular glycine in T-ALL cell lines (as opposed to glycine uptake), M+2 glycine was
244 predominant in Molt4 cells incubated with [U-¹³C]-serine (Fig. 2g). Thus, (+)SHIN2 exerts
245 potent antiproliferative effect in human T-ALL cell lines through SHMT inhibition and
246 associated depletion of both 1C units and intracellular glycine.

247 *SHIN2 shows therapeutic activity in mouse primary T-ALL in vivo*

248 SHIN2 showed potent antiproliferative effect against human T-ALL cell lines (Fig. 2 and S2)
249 and *in vivo* SHMT target engagement over several hours from a single dose (Fig 1g-i) so we
250 decided to test its antitumor properties *in vivo*. We first analyzed possible drug-induced toxicity
251 in healthy mice treated with (+)SHIN2 (200 mg/kg BID, IP) for 11 consecutive days. SHIN2
252 administration did not impact total body weight (Fig. S3a). Similar to other anti-folates, it
253 decreased hematological populations, including neutrophils, lymphocytes, monocytes and
254 eosinophils, albeit to a lesser extent than methotrexate (Fig. S3b). All of these parameters
255 returned to normal once the treatment was discontinued (Fig. S3b). We also analyzed T-cell
256 development in these mice and, consistent with the effects of SHMT inhibition in T-cell
257 proliferation (ref. 35), (+)SHIN2 treatment decreased thymus weight and cellularity, which
258 normalized after treatment discontinuation (Fig. S4a). This phenotype reflected decreased
259 thymocyte numbers across all populations (including double negative, CD4/CD8-double
260 positive, mature CD4-single positive and mature CD8-single positive), rather than alteration of
261 any specific thymocyte subpopulation (Fig.S4b-c). Thus, (+)SHIN2 is generally well tolerated
262 with modest hematological toxicity.

263 NOTCH1 is the main oncogenic driver in T-ALL, as ~60% of patients show activating
264 mutations in NOTCH1 (ref. 31). To model T-ALL in the mouse, we retrovirally transduced a
265 GFP-expressing L1601P- Δ PEST-NOTCH1 (an oncogenic form of NOTCH1 that occurs in

266 human T-ALL patients) into mouse bone marrow progenitor cells followed by transplantation in
267 secondary recipients (ref. 25,36). This well-established model leads to T-ALL development in
268 mice with high penetrance (ref. 37) and NOTCH1-induced T-ALL models have been previously
269 used to uncover the role and the therapeutic effects of a wide variety of targets in this disease
270 (ref. 25,38,39). Once the primary recipient mice developed leukemia, NOTCH1-driven leukemic
271 cells were engineered to express luciferase (ref. 25) and transplanted into a secondary cohort of
272 mice which were treated with vehicle or (+)SHIN2 (200 mg/kg BID, IP) for 11 consecutive days.
273 Notably, (+)SHIN2 treatment significantly decreased tumor burden soon after treatment
274 initiation, as assessed by either *in vivo* bioimaging (Fig. 3a-b) or FACS detection of leukemic
275 GFP-positive cells in peripheral blood (Fig. 3c). Moreover, (+)SHIN2 treatment translated into
276 extended survival, from median 16 days in control mice to 27 days in the (+)SHIN2 treated
277 group (Fig. 3d). Thus, targeting of SHMT with (+)SHIN2 shows efficacy in primary mouse T-
278 ALL.

279 ***Synergism between SHIN2 and methotrexate in human T-ALL cell lines***

280 DHFR and SHMT carry out sequential enzymatic reactions in the pathway from
281 dihydrofolate to methylene-THF. Accordingly, we were curious if inhibition of both steps might
282 have therapeutic benefits. In the human T-ALL cell line Molt4, the combination of methotrexate
283 and (+)SHIN2 suppressed proliferation more strongly than either drug alone (Fig. 4a and Fig
284 S5a), with methotrexate decreasing the IC₅₀ for (+)SHIN2 (Fig. 4b) and the IC₅₀ isobologram
285 confirming synergy (Fig. 4c and Fig. S5a-c). Synergy between (+)SHIN2 and methotrexate was
286 also observed in Molt3 and Jurkat human T-ALL cell lines (Fig S5d-e).

287 ***Synergism between SHIN2 and methotrexate in mouse T-ALL in vivo***

288 We then decided to test the *in vivo* antitumor effect of the combination of (+)SHIN2 and
289 methotrexate in our NOTCH1-driven murine T-ALL model. Here, we decided to implement a
290 less aggressive dosage regimen to reduce the probability of potential toxicity observed in mice
291 treated with both agents. Specifically, a 5-days ON and 2-days OFF treatment schedule with
292 (+)SHIN2 dosed at 200 mg/kg and methotrexate at 10 mg/kg (as shown in Fig. 5a) did not lead
293 to noticeable toxicity in healthy wild-type mice after two rounds of treatment, either in body
294 weight or hematological parameters (Fig. S6a-b) and was therefore selected for the subsequent
295 experiment in leukemic mice *in vivo*. Mice transplanted with NOTCH1-induced primary T-ALL
296 were treated for 4 weeks with (+)SHIN2 and methotrexate, alone or in combination. This
297 treatment significantly reduced tumor burden compared to vehicle treated mice, as measured by
298 *in vivo* bioimaging after one cycle of treatment (Fig. 5b-c). Importantly, long-term treatment with
299 the (+)SHIN2 and methotrexate combination significantly increased leukemic mice survival as
300 compared to vehicle alone or either drug used in monotherapy (Fig. 5d). To evaluate the
301 occurrence of a synergistic or an additive effect, we fit the data introducing an interaction term
302 using a Firth's penalized maximum likelihood bias reduction method for Cox regression,
303 obtaining a significant non-zero coefficient for the interaction term (Fig. 5e). These results
304 demonstrate that methotrexate and (+)SHIN2 synergize in prolonging survival in mouse T-ALL.

305 ***Synergism between SHIN2 and methotrexate in a patient-derived T-ALL xenograft in vivo***

306 Next, we tested the efficacy of the combination therapy of (+)SHIN2 and methotrexate in a
307 patient-derived T-ALL xenograft (PDX) *in vivo*. Mice transplanted with a luciferase-expressing
308 T-ALL PDX (PDTALL#10; (ref. 25)) were treated on a schedule resulting from the combination
309 of our previously used regimes (described in Materials and Methods). Consistent with our
310 previous results in mouse primary leukemias (Fig. 5), (+)SHIN2 treatment alone or in

311 combination with methotrexate led to decreased tumor burden as assessed by *in vivo* bioimaging
312 (Fig. 6a-b). Moreover, treatment with (+)SHIN2 as single agent significantly increased survival
313 of PDX-bearing mice, and combination of (+)SHIN2 with methotrexate led to a synergistic effect
314 with further extended survival (Fig. 6c). These results demonstrate that methotrexate and
315 (+)SHIN2 synergize in prolonging survival in mice harboring a patient-derived T-ALL xenograft
316 *in vivo*.

317 ***Methotrexate resistance sensitizes Molt4 cells to SHMT inhibition***

318 Resistance to chemotherapy is an important clinical challenge in T-ALL (ref. 22,23). Given
319 the favorable *in vivo* efficacy of the SHIN2-methotrexate combination, we decided to develop
320 methotrexate-resistant Molt4 cells to test whether such cells would retain sensitivity to SHMT
321 inhibition. To this end, Molt4 cells were cultured in increasing doses of methotrexate until we
322 achieved a derived-cell line that showed a > 2-fold increase in IC₅₀ for methotrexate (Fig. 7a).
323 Surprisingly, methotrexate-resistant cells not only remained sensitive to SHMT inhibition, but
324 actually showed enhanced sensitivity to (+)SHIN2 (4-fold decrease in IC₅₀; Fig. 7b). Thus,
325 SHMT inhibition represents a new metabolic vulnerability in methotrexate-resistant T-ALL
326 cells.

327 **Discussion**

328 Inhibition of folate metabolism and/or nucleotide biosynthesis is an important anticancer
329 strategy. The main antifolates in current clinical practice are methotrexate, which primarily
330 targets DHFR, and pemetrexed, which primarily targets thymidylate synthase (5-FU, acting as a
331 dUMP analogue, also inhibits thymidylate synthase) (ref. 1,40). The product of DHFR is THF,
332 while the substrate of thymidylate synthase is methylene-THF. The intervening chemical
333 reaction, converting THF into methylene-THF, is carried out by SHMT, which uses serine as the
334 one-carbon donor and makes glycine as an additional product. Given that SHMT sits in the folate
335 pathway directly between these two valuable anticancer targets and that the mitochondrial
336 isozyme SHMT2 is among the most consistently upregulated genes in cancer (ref. 16), there is
337 strong rationale for exploring SHMT inhibition.

338 To this end, we developed the *in vivo* active SHMT inhibitor SHIN2. Three metabolic
339 hallmarks of selective SHMT inhibition are (i) accumulation of purine intermediates
340 immediately upstream of 10-formyl-THF requiring reactions (GAR, AICAR); (ii) blockade of
341 passage of serine derived carbon into purines or dTTP as assayed by isotopic incorporation; and
342 (iii) rescue of these effects by the soluble 1C-donor formate (ref. 4,18). SHIN2 induced these
343 hallmarks of SHMT inhibition, suggesting on-target activity without significant off-target
344 activity against other folate pathway enzymes.

345 To assess pharmacodynamic effects, it is convenient to monitor circulating metabolites,
346 rather than relying on invasive tissue sampling. To this end, we took advantage of the fact that
347 SHMT both synthesizes glycine and “scrambles” uniformly ¹³C-labeled serine into partially
348 labeled serine (ref. 4). Serine and glycine are abundant in the circulation and rapidly exchange
349 between the circulation and cells, which allowed us to monitor SHMT inhibition by infusing [U-

350 ¹³C]-serine and monitoring circulating serine and glycine labeling. In this manner, we were able
351 to confirm prolonged (~ 8 h) *in vivo* SHMT inhibition by SHIN2.

352 Having proved the SHMT inhibitory effects of SHIN2 *in vivo*, we next decided to explore the
353 potential therapeutic effect of this inhibition in T-ALL. These studies were motivated by (i) the
354 sensitivity of ALL to folate/1C metabolism inhibition *in vitro* (ref. 18,27); (ii) the clinical use of
355 methotrexate as standard of care for T-ALL therapy (ref. 20,41); (iii) resistance to methotrexate
356 being a cause of treatment failure with limited alternative therapies available (ref. 20,21,41,42);
357 and (iv) the possibility for methotrexate, by depleting one of the SHMT substrates (THF) to
358 sensitize cancer cells to SHMT inhibition (Fig. 7c), much as dietary-induced 1C depletion can
359 sensitize to 5-FU (ref. 43–45). Encouragingly, we observed single agent efficacy of SHIN2 as
360 well as synergistic interaction of SHIN2 with methotrexate in decreasing tumor burden and
361 extending survival in both mouse primary leukemias and human patient-derived T-ALL
362 xenografts.

363 A striking feature of cells rendered genetically defective in mitochondrial folate metabolism
364 is glycine auxotrophy. These cells can no longer produce sufficient glycine internally and rely on
365 glycine uptake instead (ref. 4,14,19,46–50). While some solid tumor cell lines are very effective
366 at glycine uptake (ref. 5,18), we have previously found that diffuse large B cell lymphoma are
367 deficient in glycine uptake and thus sensitive to SHMT inhibition even in the presence of
368 exogenous formate (ref. 18). In T-ALL cells in culture, isotope tracing shows that a majority of
369 glycine is made by SHMT, but nevertheless formate rescues proliferation defects induced by
370 SHMT inhibition. Thus, at least in cell culture, lack of 1C units seems to be the primary
371 deficiency; however, glycine deficiency may also play a role *in vivo*.

372 Importantly, in addition to synergizing with methotrexate, SHIN2 is particularly effective in
373 cells rendered resistant to methotrexate. Mechanisms of resistance to antifolates in general, and
374 methotrexate in particular, include decreased transport mediated by the reduced folate carrier
375 (RFC, SLC19A1), altered polyglutamylation due to decreased folylpolyglutamate synthetase
376 (FPGS) activity or increased gamma glutamyl hydrolase activity (γ -GH), increased DHFR or TS
377 activity, and mutations in DHFR (ref. 40,51). Unlike methotrexate and pemetrexed, SHIN2's
378 structure is distinct from folate and its activity does not depend on polyglutamation. A logical
379 possibility is that decreases in folate transport or polyglutamation, which develop in response to
380 methotrexate exposure, decrease the intracellular pool of THF and thereby render lower doses of
381 SHIN2 effective in blocking SHMT (Fig. 7d). The cross-sensitization between methotrexate and
382 SHMT inhibition renders the contemporaneous or sequential use of these agents a promising
383 approach for leukemia treatment.

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385 Lancho and G. S. Ducker conceived the study. J. C. García-Cañaveras, O. Lancho, G. S. Ducker,
386 J. M. Ghergurovich, X. Xu, and V. da Silva-Diz conducted the experiments. S. Minuzzo and S.
387 Indraccolo generated the human T-ALL xenograft. H. Kim. and G. S. Ducker designed SHIN2.
388 H. Kim designed and oversaw the chemical synthesis strategy. J. D. Rabinowitz, D. Herranz, J.
389 C. García-Cañaveras, and O. Lancho wrote the paper.

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543 **Figure legends**

544 **Figure 1. SHIN2 inhibits SHMT *in vitro* and *in vivo*.** (a) Chemical structure. (b) Growth of
545 HCT116 cells (n=3). (c) Normalized levels of purine biosynthetic pathway intermediates in
546 HCT116 cells (24 h drug exposure at 2 μ M) (mean \pm SD, n=3). In **b** and **c**, formate concentration
547 is 1 mM and (-)SHIN2 is the inactive enantiomer. (d) Experimental design for the analysis of *in*
548 *vivo* target engagement using IP delivery of (+)SHIN2 followed by infusion of U-¹³C-serine. The
549 times in red indicate blood collection. (e) Schematic showing labeling from infused U-¹³C-serine
550 into glycine and serine via 1C/folate metabolism. (f) Plasma (+)SHIN2 concentration over time
551 after a 200 mg/kg IP dose (mean, n = 2). (g,h) Circulating serine labeling pattern upon vehicle
552 (g) or 200 mg/kg IP (+)SHIN2 (h) administration (n=2). (i) Circulating glycine M+2 fraction
553 upon vehicle or (+)SHIN2 administration (n=2).

554 **Figure 2. SHIN2 blocks growth of the human T-ALL cell line Molt4 via SHMT inhibition.**
555 (a) Growth of Molt4 cells (n=3). (b) Analysis of (+)SHIN2 effects on cell cycle in Molt4 cells
556 (48 h after treatment). Representative cell cycle histograms are shown on the panels on the left;
557 quantification is shown on the panel on the right (mean \pm SD, n=3). (c-e) Metabolite levels in
558 Molt4 cells (24 h drug exposure) (mean, n=3). In **c** and **d**, metabolites displaying a fold-change >
559 4 are highlighted in red. (f) Schematic showing the incorporation of U-¹³C-serine-derived
560 carbons into downstream products. (g) Metabolite labeling patterns in Molt4 cells after a 6 h
561 incubation with U-¹³C-serine (mean \pm SD, n=3). (+)SHIN2 concentration is 2 μ M, formate
562 concentration is 1 mM.

563 **Figure 3. SHIN2 has an antileukemic effect in T-ALL *in vivo*.** (a-b) Representative images
564 from treated mice (a) and quantification (b) of changes in tumor burden at day 3 and day 5 post-
565 treatment initiation with (+)SHIN2 (200 mg/kg, BID) as assessed by bioimaging in mice

566 allografted with NOTCH1-induced mouse leukemia cells (n=9 for vehicle; n=10 for (+)SHIN2).
567 *P* values were calculated using a two-tailed unpaired Student's t-test. (c) Changes in leukemic
568 burden at day 4 post treatment initiation with (+)SHIN2 (200 mg/kg, BID) as assessed by FACS
569 detection of leukemic GFP-positive cells in peripheral blood (n=9 for vehicle; n=10 for
570 (+)SHIN2). *P* value was calculated using a two-tailed unpaired Student's t-test. (d) Kaplan-
571 Meier survival curves of mice harboring NOTCH1-induced mouse T-ALL treated with vehicle
572 or (+)SHIN2 (200 mg/kg) for 11 days (log-rank test; ***P*<0.01) (n=9 for vehicle; n=10 for
573 (+)SHIN2).

574 **Figure 4. SHIN2 and methotrexate synergize in Molt4 cells.** (a-b) Growth of Molt4 cells
575 incubated with increasing concentrations of (+)SHIN2 in the presence of 0, 20, 30 and 40 nM
576 methotrexate (MTX) normalized to DMSO control proliferation (a) or to proliferation for the
577 same methotrexate dose in the absence of (+)SHIN2 (b) (n=3). (c) Isobologram for (+)SHIN2
578 and methotrexate showing the combinations of the drug that achieve a decrease in proliferation
579 of > 50%; purple, actual values; black line, theoretical additive effect.

580 **Figure 5. Synergistic *in vivo* antileukemic effect of SHIN2 and methotrexate in mouse**
581 **primary leukemia** (a) Dosage regimen for each of the 4 cycles of treatment. Methotrexate was
582 administered at 10 mg/kg (IP injection), (+)SHIN2 was administered at 200 mg/kg (IP injection).
583 (b-c) Representative images from five treated mice (b) and quantification (c) of changes in tumor
584 burden as assessed by bioimaging in mice allografted with NOTCH1-induced mouse leukemia
585 cells after one treatment cycle (n=10 for all groups). *P* value was calculated using one-way
586 ANOVA testing. (d) Kaplan-Meier survival curves (n=10 for all groups, log-rank test; ***P*<0.01,
587 *****P*<0.001). Blue arrows represent methotrexate injection. Red bars represent days under
588 (+)SHIN2 treatment. (e) Results of a Cox regression with Firth's penalized likelihood including

589 the terms for (+)SHIN2, methotrexate and the interaction between (+)SHIN2 and methotrexate.
590 For each parameter the actual value of the coefficient, the standard error and the *p* value (null
591 hypothesis coefficient = 0) are shown.

592 **Figure 6. Synergistic *in vivo* antileukemic effect of SHIN2 and methotrexate in a human**
593 **patient-derived T-ALL xenograft. (a-b)** Representative images from treated mice **(a)** and
594 quantification **(b)** of changes in tumor burden as assessed by bioimaging in mice xenografted
595 with a human patient-derived T-ALL xenograft at day 3 or day 7 after treatment initiation (n=12
596 for (+)SHIN2 and n=13 for the other groups). *P* value was calculated using one-way ANOVA
597 testing, *p* value for (+)SHIN2 vs (+)SHIN2 + MTX comparison was calculated using Tukey's
598 multiple comparisons test. **(c)** Kaplan-Meier survival curves (n=12 for (+)SHIN2 and n=13 for
599 the other groups, log-rank test; ****P*<0.005, *****P*<0.001). Blue arrows represent methotrexate
600 injection. Red bars represent days under (+)SHIN2 treatment.

601 **Figure 7. Methotrexate resistance sensitizes Molt4 cells to SHIN2. (a-b)** Growth of parental
602 or methotrexate (MTX)-resistant Molt4 cells incubated with increasing concentrations of
603 methotrexate **(a)** or (+)SHIN2 **(b)** (n=3). **(c)** Proposed mechanism for the synergy between
604 methotrexate and SHIN2 in T-ALL. DHFR inhibition by methotrexate decreases intracellular
605 THF and thereby sensitizes cells to SHMT inhibition. **(d)** Proposed mechanism by which
606 methotrexate resistance sensitizes to SHIN2. Decreases in folate import and polyglutamation
607 (steps highlighted in orange) promote methotrexate resistance by decreasing intracellular
608 polyglutamated-methotrexate (MTX(Glu)_n), but also decrease polyglutamated-THF (THF(Glu)_n),
609 depleting the substrate of the SHMT reaction and thereby sensitizing the cells to SHIN2.

a.

a.

a.

Day 1: morning MTX/vehicle
 night (+)SHIN2/vehicle

Day 2-4: morning (+)SHIN2/vehicle
 night (+)SHIN2/vehicle

Day 5: morning MTX/vehicle
 night rest

Day 6-7: morning rest
 night rest

e.

	Coefficient	Std Error	p value
(+)SHIN2	-1.5	0.5	0.003
MTX	-1.4	0.5	0.005
(+)SHIN2*MTX	-2.8	1.6	0.013

a.

b.

c. Synergy between methotrexate and SHIN2

d. Sensitization to SHIN2 induced by resistance to methotrexate

Supplementary Information

SHMT inhibition is effective and synergizes with methotrexate in T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia

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Supplementary Materials and Methods

Proliferation assays

Standard proliferation assays were conducted in 96 well plates and relative cell number measured using resazurin sodium salt. For adherent cell lines, 3×10^3 cells were plated in each well in 100 μ L of media were allowed to adhere overnight. Media containing inhibitor (0.5% DMSO final concentration) was added the next day and cell growth was assessed via fluorescence intensity using a Synergy HT plate reader (BioTek Instruments) at 48 hours post-treatment. For suspension cell lines, 10^4 cells were plated in each well in 90 μ L of media and allowed to rest for 2 h. 10 μ L of a 10x solution of inhibitor in media (0.5% DMSO final concentration) were added and cell growth was assessed via fluorescence intensity using a Synergy HT plate reader (BioTek Instruments) at 48 hours post-treatment.

Cell cycle and apoptosis analyses

Cell cycle and apoptosis were analyzed in cells treated during 48 h with vehicle (DMSO) or (+) SHIN2 (IC₅₀ respective to each cell line). PI/RNase Staining Buffer (BD Pharmingen) was used to analyze cell cycle distribution. Apoptosis was quantified with the PE-AnnexinV Apoptosis

Detection Kit I (BD Pharmingen). Stained cells were analyzed using an Attune NxT Flow Cytometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and data was analyzed using the FlowJo software (BD).

Flow cytometry analysis of T-cell development

Single cell suspensions of thymocytes were obtained by pressing the thymus through a 40 μ m filter. For flow cytometry-based analysis of discrete stages of T-cell development, cells were stained with anti-mouse fluorochrome-conjugated antibodies as follows (clone names are provided in parentheses): CD8a phycoerythrin (PE) (1:200, 53-6.7, BD Pharmingen), CD4 APC (1:1000, RM4-5, BD Pharmingen), CD44 eFluor 450 (1:200, IM7, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and CD25 Alexa Fluor 488 (1:1000, 7D4, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Total thymus populations were represented in a CD4 versus CD8a plot and CD4/CD8 DP ($CD4^+CD8a^+$), CD4SP ($CD4^+CD8a^-$), CD8SP ($CD4^-CD8a^+$) and CD4/CD8 DN ($CD4^-CD8a^-$) populations were gated. Then CD4/CD8 DN were plotted in a CD44 versus CD25 plot to characterize DN1 ($CD4^-CD8a^-CD44^+CD25^-$), DN2 ($CD4^-CD8a^-CD44^+CD25^+$), DN3 ($CD4^-CD8a^-CD44^-CD25^+$) and DN4 ($CD4^-CD8a^-CD44^-CD25^-$) populations. Flow cytometry data were collected on an Attune NxT Flow Cytometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and analyzed with FlowJo software (BD).

Measurement of hematological parameters

Blood collected from mice treated with (+)SHIN2 and/or methotrexate was analyzed using an Element HT5 Veterinary Hematology Analyzer (Heska).

Cell metabolism studies

HCT116 cells were plated in 6 cm tissue culture dishes and grown to 60% confluency. At the start of an experiment, the appropriate media was added to cells, which included vehicle (DMSO 0.5%), or (+) or (-) SHIN2 2 μ M and/or sodium formate 1 mM. Total incubation time was 24 h

and fresh media was added 6 h before metabolome extraction for untargeted metabolomics. Cell number was estimated by the measurement of packed cell volume (PCV).

U-¹³C-serine was purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories. Serine isotopically labeled media was prepared from glucose, glycine and serine-free RPMI media (R9660, Teknova) and supplemented with 10% dialyzed FBS, 100 U/ml penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin.

Human T-ALL cell lines (i.e. Molt3, Molt4 and Jurkat) were plated in 6 cm tissue culture dishes at 10⁶ cells/mL in the appropriate media, which included vehicle (DMSO 0.5%), or (+)SHIN2 2 µM and/or sodium formate 1 mM. Total incubation time was 24 h. 6 h before metabolome extraction, cell density was adjusted to 2x10⁶ cells/mL in fresh media. In the case of incubations with U-¹³C-serine, serine isotopically labeled media was used for the 6 h incubation. Cell number was counted directly using Trypan blue and the Countess system (Invitrogen).

Metabolite extraction

For HC116 cells, media was removed by aspiration and the cells washed once with room temperature PBS. Metabolome extraction was performed by the addition of 800 µL of ice cold extraction solvent (40:40:20 acetonitrile:methanol:water + 0.5% formic acid). After a 1 min incubation on ice, the extract was neutralized by the addition of NH₄HCO₃. The samples were incubated at -20 °C for ~30 min, at which point the wells were scraped and the extract transferred to Eppendorf tubes and centrifuged (15 min, 16000 rpm, 4 °C). The resulting supernatant was frozen on dry ice and kept at -80 °C until LC-MS analysis.

For T-ALL cells, cell suspensions were transferred to 1.5 mL tubes and pelleted (30 s, 6000 rpm, room temperature). Media was removed by aspiration and the pellet washed once with room temperature PBS. Metabolome extraction was performed by the addition of 75 µL of ice cold solvent (40:40:20 ACN:MeOH:H₂O + 0.5% formic acid) to the pellet. After a 5 min incubation

on ice, acid was neutralized by the addition of NH_4HCO_3 . After centrifugation (15 min, 16000 rpm, 4 °C), the resulting supernatant was transferred to a clean tube, frozen on dry ice and kept at -80 °C until LC-MS analysis.

For serum, 5 μL were mixed with 150 μL -20 °C 80:20 methanol:water, vortexed, and immediately centrifuged at 16,000 x g for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was collected for LC-MS analysis.

LC-MS-based untargeted metabolomics

Extracts were analyzed using a quadrupole-orbitrap mass spectrometer (Q Exactive, Thermo Fisher Scientific) coupled to hydrophilic interaction chromatography via electrospray ionization. Liquid chromatography separation was on a XBridge BEH Amide column (2.1 mm \times 150 mm, 2.5 μm particle size; Waters) using a gradient of solvent A (20 mM ammonium acetate, 20 mM ammonium hydroxide in 95:5 water:acetonitrile, pH 9.45) and solvent B (acetonitrile). Flow rate was 150 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, column temperature was 25 °C, autosampler temperature was 5 °C and injection volume was 10 μL . The liquid chromatography gradient was: 0 min, 90% B; 2 min, 85% B; 3 min, 75% B; 7 min, 75% B; 8 min, 70% B; 9 min, 70% B; 10 min, 50% B; 12 min, 50% B; 13 min, 25% B; 14 min, 25% B; 16 min, 0% B; 21 min, 0% B; 22 min, 90% B; 25 min, 90% B. Autosampler temperature was 5 °C and injection volume was 10 μL . The mass spectrometer was operated in negative-ion mode to scan from m/z 70 to 1,000 at 1 Hz and a resolving power of 140,000. Data were analyzed using the EI-MAVEN software (v 0.2.4, Elucidata), with compounds identified based on exact mass and retention time match to commercial standards. Isotopic labeling of metabolites arising from incubation with $\text{U-}^{13}\text{C}$ -serine were corrected for natural abundance, as previously described (ref. 52). Adherent cell metabolite abundances were normalized by packed cell volume; suspension cells to cell count.

Chemical synthesis of SHIN2

Commercially available starting materials were used without further purification. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Varian or Bruker 500, 400, or 300 MHz spectrometers and referenced to solvent peaks. Coupling constants (J) are reported in hertz, chemical shifts are reported in δ (ppm) as either s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), quin (quintet), dd (doublet of doublets), or m (multiplet).

Synthesis of 3-bromo-5-(1-hydroxy-2-methylpropyl) benzonitrile:

Into a 5000 mL 3-necked round-bottom flask purged and maintained with an inert atmosphere of nitrogen, was placed 3,5-dibromobenzonitrile (300 g, 1150 mmol, 1 equiv), THF (2500 mL). This was followed by the addition of $i\text{-PrMgCl}$ (579 mL, 5630 mmol, 1 equiv, 2M) dropwise with stirring at 4 °C. The resulting solution was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. To this was added a solution of 2-methylpropanal (91.2 g, 1260 mmol, 1.1 equiv) in THF (700 mL) dropwise with stirring at room temperature. The resulting solution was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. One more reaction was repeated in parallel, combined and worked up together. The reaction was then quenched by the addition of 1000 mL of NH_4Cl (aq). The resulting solution was extracted with 3x2000 mL of ethyl acetate and the organic layers combined and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and concentrated. The residue was applied onto a silica gel column with ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (1:10). This resulted in 510 g (87.27%) of 3-bromo-5-(1-hydroxy-2-methylpropyl) benzonitrile as yellow oil. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ - 3-bromo-5-(1-hydroxy-2-methylpropyl)

benzonitrile: ^1H NMR (300 MHz, Chloroform- d) δ 7.72 (d, J = 11.0 Hz, 1H), 7.62 – 7.51 (m, 1H), 4.48 (d, J = 5.9 Hz, 1H), 0.92 (dd, J = 14.8, 6.8 Hz, 6H).

Synthesis of 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzonitrile:

Into a 3000 mL 3-necked round-bottom flask purged and maintained with an inert atmosphere of nitrogen, was placed 3-bromo-5-(1-hydroxy-2-methylpropyl)benzonitrile (255 g, 1000 mmol, 1 equiv) and acetone (2500 mL). This was followed by the addition of Jones reagent (294 mL) dropwise with stirring at room temperature. The resulting solution was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. This reaction was repeated one time and worked up together. The reaction was then quenched by the addition of 1000 mL of water. The resulting solution was extracted with 3x1000 mL of ethyl acetate and the organic layers combined and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and concentrated. The residue was applied onto a silica gel column with ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (1:10). This resulted in 430 g (84.98%) of 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzonitrile as a white solid. H-NMR-3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzonitrile: ^1H NMR (300 MHz, Chloroform- d) δ 8.29 (t, J = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.15 (t, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.97 (t, J = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 3.52 – 3.43 (m, 1H), 1.26 (d, J = 6.9 Hz, 6H).

Synthesis of 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoic acid:

Into a 2000 mL round-bottom flask, was placed 1-bromo-3-isocyano-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzene (143 g, 567 mmol, 1 equiv) in MeOH (500 mL), NaOH (541 mL, 2160 mmol, 4 M). The resulting solution was stirred for overnight at 90 °C. The reaction repeated two times. The resulting mixture was concentrated. The pH value of the solution was adjusted to 6 with HCl (12 M). The solids were collected by filtration. The solid was dried under infrared light. This resulted in 460 g (99.71%) of 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoic acid as a white solid. H-NMR-3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoic: ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 8.39 (t, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 8.23 (t, J = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 8.16 (t, J = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 3.72 – 3.63 (m, 1H), 1.11 (d, J = 6.6 Hz, 6H).

Synthesis of methyl 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoate:

Into a 10 L 3-necked round-bottom flask, was placed 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoic acid (460 g, 1700 mmol, 1 equiv) in MeOH (4500 mL), H₂SO₄ (500 mL, 0.510 mmol) was added dropwise with stirring at room temperature. The resulting solution was stirred overnight at 80 °C. The resulting mixture was concentrated. The reaction was poured into 200 g of crushed ice. The solids were collected by filtration. The solid was dried under infrared light. This resulted in 460 g (95.08%) of methyl 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoate as a white solid. H-NMR-3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoate: ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 8.40 – 8.36 (m, 2H), 8.28 (t, J = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 3.91 (s, 3H), 3.82 – 3.63 (m, 1H), 1.11 (d, J = 6.6 Hz, 6H).

Synthesis of methyl 3-bromo-5-(1, 1-diisocyano-3-methylbut-1-en-2-yl) benzoate:

Into a 2000 mL 3-necked round-bottom flask, was placed methyl 3-bromo-5-(2-methylpropanoyl) benzoate (115 g, 403 mmol, 1 equiv) in HOAc (500 mL), diisocyanomethane (133 g, 2020 mmol, 5 equiv) and HMDS (197 g, 1220 mmol, 3 equiv) was added. The resulting solution was stirred for 5 h at 80 °C. This reaction is repeated in parallel for three times and worked up together. The reaction mixture was poured into 600 g of water/ice. The solids were collected by filtration. The solid was dried under infrared light. This resulted in 410 g (76.28%) of methyl 3-bromo-5-(1, 1-diisocyano-3-methylbut-1-en-2-yl) benzoate as an orange solid. ¹H NMR-methyl 3-bromo-5-(1, 1-diisocyano-3-methylbut-1-en-2-yl) benzoate: ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 8.21 (t, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.94 (dt, J = 7.1, 1.6 Hz, 2H), 3.91 (s, 3H), 3.35 – 3.26 (m, 2H), 1.10 (d, J = 6.6 Hz, 6H).

Synthesis of methyl 3-[6-amino-5-cyano-4-isopropyl-3-methyl-1H-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazol-4-yl]-5-bromobenzoate:

Into a 1000 mL 3-necked round-bottom flask, was placed methyl 3-bromo-5-(1,1-dicyano-3-methylbut-1-en-2-yl) benzoate (50 g, 150 mmol, 1 equiv) in dioxane (200 mL) and EtOH (200 mL), piperidine (14 g, 0.16 mmol) and 3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (15 g, 0.15 mmol) was added. The resulting solution was stirred for overnight at 65 °C. The reaction was repeated seven times. The resulting mixture was concentrated. The residue was applied onto a silica gel column with ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (1:2). The crude product was purified by recrystallization with ethyl acetate. This resulted in 220 g (42.49%) of methyl 3-[6-amino-5-cyano-4-isopropyl-3-methyl-1H-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazol-4-yl]-5-bromobenzoate as a white solid. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 12.24 (s, 1H), 7.96 (t, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.87 (s, 1H), 7.74 (t, J = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.00 (s, 2H), 3.86 (s, 3H), 2.79 – 2.70 (m, 1H), 1.78 (s, 3H), 0.90 (d, J = 6.6 Hz, 3H), 0.78 (d, J = 6.6 Hz, 3H).

Synthesis of 6-amino-4-[3-bromo-5-(hydroxymethyl)phenyl]-4-isopropyl-3-methyl-1H-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole-5-carbonitrile:

Into a 1000 mL 3-necked round-bottom flask, was placed methyl 3-[6-amino-5-cyano-4-isopropyl-3-methyl-1H-pyrano [2, 3-c] pyrazol-4-yl]-5-bromobenzoate (50 g, 116 mmol, 1 equiv), THF (500 mL). This was followed by the addition of LiAlH₄ (8.8 g, 232 mmol, 2 equiv) in portions at room temperature. The resulting solution was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. Four reactions were repeated in parallel and worked up together. The reaction was then quenched by the addition of 10 mL of water. The pH value of the solution was adjusted to 6 with HCl (1 M). The resulting

solution was extracted with 3x1000 mL of ethyl acetate and the organic layers combined and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The residue was applied onto a silica gel column with ethyl acetate. This resulted in 150 g (80.21%) of 6-amino-4-[3-bromo-5-(hydroxymethyl)phenyl]-4-isopropyl-3-methyl-1H-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole-5-carbonitrile as a white solid. ¹H-NMR-6-amino-4-[3-bromo-5-(hydroxymethyl)phenyl]-4-isopropyl-3-methyl-1H-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole-5-carbonitrile: ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 12.18 (s, 1H), 7.36 (s, 1H), 7.29 (d, J = 1.8 Hz, 2H), 6.88 (s, 2H), 5.33 (t, J = 5.7 Hz, 1H), 4.48 (d, J = 5.7 Hz, 2H), 2.75 – 2.66 (m, 1H), 1.73 (s, 3H), 0.89 (d, J = 6.3 Hz, 3H), 0.76 (d, J = 6.3 Hz, 3H).

Synthesis of SHIN2 (6-amino-4-[3-(hydroxymethyl)-5-(5-hydroxypent-1-yn-1-yl)phenyl]-3-methyl-4-(propan-2-yl)-1H,4H-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole-5-carbonitrile):

Into a 40 mL round-bottom flask purged and maintained with an inert atmosphere of nitrogen, was placed 6-amino-4-[3-bromo-5-(hydroxymethyl)phenyl]-3-methyl-4-(propan-2-yl)-1H,4H-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole-5-carbonitrile (3 g, 7.44 mmol, 1 equiv), pent-4-yn-1-ol (1.25 g, 14.9 mmol, 2 equiv), DMF (15 mL, 0.205 mmol, 0.03 equiv), Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂ (0.52 g, 0.744 mmol, 0.1 equiv), CuI (0.28 g, 1.49 mmol, 0.2 equiv), Et₃N (2.26 g, 22.3 mmol, 3 equiv). The resulting solution was stirred for 1.5 h at 100 °C. And 35 reactions were repeated in parallel and worked up together. The resulting mixture was concentrated. The residue was applied onto a silica gel column with ethyl

acetate. The crude oil product (purity>90%) was slurried in ethyl acetate at room temperature for 4 h, and then filtered. This resulted (filter cake) in 45 g (42.52%) of SHIN2 as an off-white solid. H-NMR-SHIN2: ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 12.11 (s, 1H), 7.24 (s, 1H), 7.16 (d, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 6.83 (s, 2H), 5.23(t, J = 6 Hz, 3H), 4.54 – 4.45(m, 3H), 3.54 – 3.32 (m, 2H), 2.76 – 2.67 (m, 1H), 2.50 – 2.42 (m, 3H), 1.72 – 1.64 (m, 5H), 0.90 (d, J = 6.3 Hz, 3H), 0.77 (d, J = 6.3 Hz, 3H).

Chiral resolution: SHIN2 was separated by PREP-CHIRAL-HPLC with the following conditions: column: Lux Amylose-1 (2 x 250 mm); gradient: 20% ethanol/ CO_2 , 100 bar, 70 mL/min; detector, UV 220 nm.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1, related to Fig.1 SHIN2 inhibits SHMT *in vitro*. (a) Growth of WT, Δ SHMT1 and Δ SHMT2 HCT116 cells incubated with increasing concentrations of (+)SHIN2 ($n=3$). (b-d) Metabolite levels in HCT116 cells (24 h drug exposure at 2 μ M) (mean, $n=3$). Metabolites displaying a fold-change > 4 are highlighted in red.

Figure S2, related to Fig.2. SHIN2 blocks growth of human T-ALL cell lines via SHMT inhibition. (a) IC₅₀ values for methotrexate across several cell lines grouped by cancer type based on TGCA classification and ordered by median IC₅₀ value (data obtained from www.cancerrxgene.org) (ref. 27). (b) IC₅₀ values for the SHMT1/2 inhibitor (+)2 across several cell lines grouped by cancer type based on TGCA classification and order by median IC₅₀ value (data obtained from ref. 18, data shown only for cells common to those included in panel A and with at least 5 cell lines per group. In **a** and **b** the number of cell lines per cancer type is indicated in parenthesis. (c) Western blots of SHMT2 (showing two different exposure time points) and β-ACTIN in normal hematological cells (i.e. human thymus, peripheral blood mononuclear cells and peripheral blood CD4⁺ T cells) and various human T-ALL cell lines. (d) mRNA levels of *Shmt1* and *Shmt2* upon NOTCH1 inhibition with the DBZ gamma-secretase inhibitor in mouse T-ALL *in vivo* (taken from ref. 25) (FDR: * <0.05 , ** <0.005). (e) mRNA levels of *Shmt1* and *Shmt2* upon N-Me deletion in mouse T-ALL *in vivo* (taken from ref. 33) (FDR: ** <0.005 , *** <0.005). (f) Growth of the human T-ALL cell lines Molt4, Molt3, Jurkat and HPBALL (n=3). (g-h) Apoptosis (g, p value calculated using an unpaired two-tailed Student's t test) and cell cycle effects (h) in a panel of T-ALL cell lines treated with (+)SHIN2 for 48 h (mean \pm SD, n=3) (i-j) Metabolite levels in Molt3 (i) and Jurkat cells (j) (24 h drug exposure) (mean, n=3). Metabolites displaying a fold-change > 4 are highlighted in red. (+)SHIN2 concentration is 2 μ M, formate concentration is 1 mM.

Figure S3, related to Fig.3. SHIN2 treatment leads to reversible heme toxicity. (a) Body weight of mice treated with vehicle alone or (+)SHIN2 for 11 consecutive days (highlighted in red) and during 11 days after treatment discontinuation (day 0-12, n=12 per group, day 12-22 n=6 per group). **(b)** Hematological parameters of mice treated with vehicle alone or (+)SHIN2 for 11 consecutive days and 11 days after treatment discontinuation (n=12 per group at day 12; n=6 per group at day 22). *P* values were calculated using an unpaired two-tailed Student's *t* test.

Figure S4, related to Fig.3. SHIN2 treatment leads to reversible effects on T-cell development. (a) Thymus weight of mice treated with vehicle alone or (+)SHIN2 for 11 consecutive or 11 days after treatment discontinuation. (b-c) Immunophenotypic analyses of thymocyte populations from mice treated with vehicle alone or (+)SHIN2 for 11 consecutive or 11 days after treatment discontinuation. *P* values were calculated using an unpaired two-tailed Student's *t* test, *n*=6 per group.

Figure S5, related to Fig.4. SHIN2 and methotrexate synergize in human T-ALL cell lines. (a-b) Growth of Molt4 cells incubated with increasing concentrations of methotrexate (MTX) in the presence of 0, 10, 40 and 80 nM (+)SHIN2 normalized to DMSO control proliferation (a) or to the same dose of methotrexate without (+)SHIN2 (b) (n=3). (c) Relative cell growth of Molt4 cells (mean, n=3). (d-e) Growth of Molt3 (d) and Jurkat (e) cells incubated with increasing concentrations of (+)SHIN2 in the presence of the indicated methotrexate concentration normalized to DMSO control proliferation (left, n=3) or to the same dose of methotrexate without (+)SHIN2 (center, n=3), and isobologram for (+)SHIN2 and methotrexate showing the combinations of the drug that achieve a decrease in proliferation > 50%.

Figure S6, related to Fig.5. Minimal toxicity using SHIN2 and methotrexate combination treatment. (a) Body weight of mice treated with vehicle alone, methotrexate or a combination of methotrexate and (+)SHIN2 during two cycles of treatment (highlighted in purple) (n=3 per group). Methotrexate treatment (10 mg/kg) is represented by blue arrows. (+)SHIN2 treatment (200 mg/kg) is represented by red bars. **(b)** Hematological parameters of mice treated with vehicle

alone, methotrexate or a combination of methotrexate and (+)SHIN2 during two cycles of treatment (n=3 per group). Statistical significance was calculated using ANOVA test and the *p* values for paired comparisons were calculated using Tukey's multiple comparisons post-hoc test.

Supplementary References

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